

How to Find Things to Do in Tokyo

Tokyo is one of the world's most exciting travel destinations. However, the city is so vast that finding things to do in Tokyo can sometimes be harder than you'd expect. In this article, you can find 3 ways to find things to do in Tokyo for your upcoming trip.

1. Take to the Internet

When it comes to researching a travel destination, the internet is really the best place to start. Sites like [Metatrip](#) can be really useful when looking for unique and exciting attractions. Online research can also help you to find the best deal on attraction and book a lot of tickets in advance.

2. Read Some Travel Guides

Read books, really? Although reading travel guides that you can find in popular bookstores might seem like a slightly outdated concept, they're often really useful for finding out about new and interesting attractions. When buying guides, check the publishing dates to ensure that the guide isn't old and outdated.

3. Ask the Locals

One of the most fun and unique ways to find things to do in Tokyo is to ask the locals. Although English speaking isn't that common in Tokyo, lots of locals do have some knowledge of the language and love to practice and talk with foreigners. Locals often know the best places to visit, and they may also know about hidden spots that aren't featured in any guidebooks.